

Regional Hemoglobinopathy Trends in Eastern Maharashtra using Advanced HPLC DiagnosticsShriram Chopade¹, Rajesh Kate², Snehal Tale³, Aishwarya Mantri⁴, Dilip Sarate⁵¹Assistant Professor, Department of Pathology, Government Medical College Akola, Maharashtra, India²Associate Professor, Department of Pathology, Government Medical College Akola, Maharashtra, India³Senior Resident, Department of Pathology, Government Medical College Akola, Maharashtra, India⁴Assistant Professor, Department of Pathology, Pacific Institute of Medical Sciences, Udaipur, Rajasthan, India⁵Professor and HOD, Department of Pathology, Government Medical College Akola, Maharashtra, India

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Abstract:

Introduction: Hemoglobinopathies, a group of inherited genetic diseases affecting haemoglobin, are a global public health concern, with a prevalence of 7% among carriers worldwide. Conditions such as β -thalassemia and sickle cell anaemia are common in India, with significant regional and ethnic variability. High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC) has emerged as a reliable diagnostic tool for identifying haemoglobin variants. This study aimed to evaluate the prevalence of hemoglobinopathies in anaemic patients from Eastern Maharashtra.

Materials and Methods: A retrospective study was conducted at a tertiary health centre in Eastern Maharashtra, analysing data from January 2019 to December 2023. 15,620 anaemic patients (Hb <11 g/dL) underwent HPLC testing using the BIO-RAD variant haemoglobin testing system. Demographic details and HPLC results were collected, and qualitative and quantitative data were statistically analysed.

Results: The prevalence of hemoglobinopathies was 13.24%, with a female predominance (60.93%). Sickle cell trait (7.14%) was the most common hemoglobinopathy, followed by β -thalassemia trait (2.98%). Other variants were also identified, including the HbE trait (0.02%) and rare double heterozygous forms. The highest prevalence occurred in the 21–30 years age group (35.02%), with declining rates in older age groups.

Conclusion: Hemoglobinopathies are significant contributors to anaemia in Eastern Maharashtra. HPLC proved effective for accurate and rapid diagnosis, underscoring the importance of systematic screening and genetic counselling in high-risk regions to reduce the burden of hereditary anaemias.

Keywords: Hemoglobinopathies, HPLC, Anemia.

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Introduction

Hemoglobinopathies encompass a range of genetic disorders that affect haemoglobin, a fundamental component of red blood cells. These disorders are recognised as the most prevalent inherited single-gene conditions on a global scale. The etiology of hemoglobinopathies is linked to mutations in the amino acid sequences of globin genes [1].

According to data from the World Health Organization (WHO), approximately 7% of the global population are carriers of haemoglobin disorders. This statistic underscores the significance of hemoglobinopathies as a major public health concern. [2]. The prevalence of these disorders is exceptionally high in India, where the rate of substantial hemoglobinopathies is recorded at 1.2 per 1,000 live births, leading to an annual estimate of 32,400 newborns affected by

haemoglobin disorders [3]. The clinical manifestations associated with these disorders vary significantly, ranging from asymptomatic presentations to instances of severe anemia that necessitates regular blood transfusions and various potential complications that contribute significantly to morbidity and mortality [1]. Consequently, early identification and accurate diagnosis are imperative for mitigating the incidence of hemoglobinopathies. High-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) is increasingly utilised as a confirmatory diagnostic method for hemoglobinopathies [4].

The prevalence of various hemoglobinopathies exhibits significant regional and ethnic variability. Notably, β -thalassemia prevalence is 6.5% in Punjab, 8.4% in Tamil Nadu, 4.3% in southern India, and 3.5% in Bengal [5]. Furthermore, it

exhibits elevated prevalence rates among specific communities, including Sindhi, Luvana, various tribal groups, and Rajputs. In Gujarat, the incidence ranges from 10% to 15%, illustrating the geographical heterogeneity of prevalence [5]. A high prevalence of sickle cell anaemia is observed, particularly in Madhya Pradesh, Chhattisgarh, and Odisha, with carrier frequencies reaching 20–30% in tribal populations.

This study aims to assess the prevalence of various hemoglobinopathies in the Eastern Maharashtra region to develop early intervention strategies for their identification, diagnosis, and prevention in forthcoming generations. Additionally, the study evaluates the effectiveness of HPLC in detecting these haemoglobin disorders, recognising that many medical centres in India currently employ HPLC analysis for carrier detection in various hemoglobinopathies.

Materials and Methods

This study was conducted at a tertiary health care centre in Eastern Maharashtra. A retrospective data analysis evaluated the number of cases diagnosed with various hemoglobinopathies through High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC) over five years from January 2019 to December 2023. Demographic details and HPLC results were extracted from patient records for analysis. A total of 15620 samples indicated a diagnosis of hemolytic anaemia (Hb <11 g/dL) among patients who sought antenatal or voluntary premarital

checkups, as well as those presenting with a clinical history and complete blood count (CBC) findings. Accordingly, all of these patients were subjected to HPLC testing. For CBC, 3 ml blood was collected in an ethylene diamine tetrachloride acetate (EDTA) vacutainer and analysed in a 3-part differential automated cell counter on the same day.

The HPLC samples were collected in an EDTA vacutainer and analysed within one week. All samples were evaluated utilising the BIO-RAD HPLC variant haemoglobin testing system, which functions based on the principle of cation exchange. In conjunction with this system, the β -thalassemia short program recorder pack was employed to quantify the levels of haemoglobin types A, A2, F, and other haemoglobin variants.

The data collected were systematically compiled and analysed. Qualitative variables were expressed as percentages, while quantitative variables were represented as percentages or as means accompanied by standard deviations.

Results

The analysis of hemoglobinopathies in anaemic patients revealed significant variation across age groups. The highest prevalence (35.02%) was observed among individuals aged 21–30, followed by 31–40 (19.08%) and 11–20 (13.98%).

Older age groups showed a declining trend, with frequencies of 6.02% in the 61–70 age group and only 0.99% in those aged 81–90 (Table 1).

Table 1: Age-wise distribution of the population with hemoglobinopathies

Age Group	Frequency	Percentage
1-10	33	1.98%
11-20	234	13.98%
21-30	585	35.02%
31-40	319	19.08%
41-50	185	11.08%
51-60	131	7.82%
61-70	101	6.02%
71-80	67	4.03%
81-90	17	0.99%

The prevalence of hemoglobinopathies is observed to be higher in females, accounting for 60.93%, compared to 39.07% in males (Table 2).

Table 2: Gender-wise distribution of the population with hemoglobinopathies

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	653	39.08%
Female	1018	60.92%

Hemoglobinopathies were found in 13.24% of the population. Significant proportions were attributed to sickle cell trait (7.14%) and β thalassemia trait (β TT) (2.98%). Sickle cell disease (2.68%) and beta-thalassemia major (0.21%) were less common. Hb E trait was prevalent in 0.02% of the population. Rare variants like Double

Heterozygous for HbS and Beta thalassemia, Double Heterozygous for HbS and Hb E, Double Heterozygous for Hb E and β TT and Double Heterozygous for HbS and Hb D Punjab accounted for a small fraction, i.e., 0.16%, 0.03%, 0.01% and 0.01%, respectively, highlighting the diversity of genetic disorders in this region (Table 3).

Table 3: Prevalence of various hemoglobinopathies in the study population

Hemoglobin Variant	Frequency	Percentage
Free of Hemoglobinopathies	10949	86.76%
Sickle cell trait	901	7.14%
Beta Thalassemia trait	376	2.98%
Sickle cell Disease	337	2.68%
Beta Thalassemia major	26	0.21%
Double Heterozygous for HbS and Beta thalassemia	20	0.16%
Double Heterozygous for HbS and Hb E	4	0.03%
Hb E Trait	3	0.02%
Double Heterozygous for Hb E and Beta Thalassemia Trait	2	0.01%
Double Heterozygous for HbS and Hb D Punjab	2	0.01%

Discussion

Hemoglobinopathies constitute a significant public health concern on a global scale, particularly in India, which faces a considerable burden on its healthcare and financial resources. Understanding the prevalence of these lifelong disorders through regional studies is essential, as hemoglobinopathies exhibit geographic variation. Early and accurate diagnosis of hemoglobinopathies is critical, as it can prevent clinically significant conditions and alleviate the associated economic and psychological burdens. In light of this, the present study was conducted to ascertain the prevalence of various hemoglobinopathies in a city located in Eastern Maharashtra. HPLC is the standard diagnostic method for haemoglobin disorders in most centres across India. It is recommended for routine screening of various hemoglobinopathies, particularly in laboratories with high throughput capabilities.

In the present study, 12,620 samples were analysed utilising HPLC and 1,671 patients were diagnosed with various hemoglobinopathies, corresponding to 13.24% of the total cases.

In a similar study conducted by Ganesh B et al. [11], a prevalence of 14.67% was reported within a tribal population. Furthermore, our findings are consistent with the prevalence of hemoglobinopathy reported in northern India, which is approximately 12.5%. A study by Pathak V et al. [7] conducted in Kota, Rajasthan, revealed a slightly elevated prevalence rate of 15.9%. Singh V et al. [1]. Reported an even higher rate of 20.12% in western Maharashtra. Additionally, studies by Philip et al. [15] and Gupta et al. [14] noted prevalence rates of 15.8% and 14.3% among anaemic patients in the Pune region of Maharashtra. Balgir S et al. [12] documented a significantly higher prevalence of 65.7% in Orissa, while Mondal and Mandal [8] reported a prevalence of 12.17% in West Bengal. Our findings demonstrated a female predominance, with 60.93% of the cases being female compared to 39.07% male. This is in alignment with the results of other studies conducted by Pathak V et al. [7], Singh et

al. [1], and Anusha R et al. [10]. However, in contrast to our findings, Kumar et al. and Patel et al. observed a male predominance within their respective studies.

The age group with the highest prevalence in our study was 21–30 years, followed by the 31–40 years and 11–20 years age groups, which corroborates observations made by Pathak V et al. [7]

Haemoglobin S (HbS) represents the most prevalent variant of haemoglobin globally. This beta-chain variant is the result of a single amino acid substitution, wherein the polar amino acid glutamate is replaced by the nonpolar amino acid valine at the sixth position of the beta-globin chain. Under conditions of low oxygen tension, red blood cells that contain HbS undergo a morphological transformation from an oval shape to a sickle shape. In the present study, the highest prevalence was noted in cases of sickle cell trait, which accounted for 7.14% while sickle cell disease exhibited a prevalence rate of 2.68%. Similarly, in a study conducted by Balgir RS et al. [12], the most common hemoglobinopathies were sickle cell trait (29.8%) and sickle cell disease (7.5%). Singh et al. [1] found the prevalence of HbS as 2.14% (the second most common hemoglobinopathy found in their study) lower than the present study. Biswas et al. [13] found even lower prevalence rates of 1.23%. Mondal and Mandal [8] found 0.98%, and Balgir RS et al. [12] found a 9.13% prevalence rate.

Beta thalassemia trait (β TT) was identified as the second most prevalent hemoglobinopathy in the current study, with a prevalence rate of 2.98%. In alignment with these findings, Balgir et al. [12] reported a prevalence of 18.2% for beta thalassemia trait, establishing it as the second most common hemoglobinopathy in their investigation. Most existing literature highlights β TT as the primary abnormality. The proportion of thalassemia trait was 11.5% in a study conducted by Pathak V et al. [7]. Singh et al. [1] documented a prevalence of 14.27% for β TT. In contrast, Philip et al. [15] reported a prevalence of 10.49%. Furthermore, Gupta et al. [14] observed a prevalence of 9.53%,

and Biswas et al. [13] noted a prevalence of 8.03%. Mondal and Mandal [8] reported a prevalence of 4.60% in rural regions of Bengal.

Beta thalassemia major had a prevalence of 0.21% with 26 cases in the present study while Balgir RS et al [12] reported prevalence of thalassemia major as 5.3% in their study.

In the present study, 20 cases (0.16%) were found with double heterozygosity for beta-thalassemia and HbS. A similar prevalence was found in studies by Pathak V et al. [7] (0.9%), Philip et al. [15] (0.48%), and Gupta et al. [14] (1.5%).

Haemoglobin E is a variant of the beta-globin chain, characterised by the substitution of glutamate with a lysine at position 26. Hemoglobin E typically elutes within the A2 window [1]. In the current study, the prevalence of individuals with the Hb E trait was identified at 0.02% (3 cases). In contrast, the prevalence of double heterozygous individuals for both Hb S and Hb E was observed at 0.03% (4 cases). Furthermore, the prevalence of double heterozygous individuals for Hb E and beta-thalassemia trait was recorded at 0.01% (2 cases).

In a study conducted by Singh et al. [1], Hb E emerged as the third most prevalent abnormality, with a prevalence rate of 1.44%. Balgir et al. [12] reported a rate of 0.9%, while Mondal and Mandal [8] documented a prevalence of 3.36%. Philip et al. [15] similarly reported a prevalence of 1.31%.

HbD is a variant of the beta chain characterised by a single amino acid substitution at position 121, wherein a glutamine residue replaces a glutamic acid residue. In India, HbD is predominantly observed in Punjab, which is designated as HbD Punjab. Another variant, HbD Iran, results from a single amino acid substitution at position 22 of the beta-globin chain, where glutamate is substituted with glutamine.

On CE-HPLC, HbD Iran elutes in the A2 window, while HbD Punjab elutes in the D window. The HPLC method allows for accurate differentiation between HbD Punjab and HbD Iran [1]. A study by Singh et al. [1] reported a prevalence rate of 0.48%, whereas Mondal and Mandal et al. [8] documented a prevalence rate of 0.09% for Hb D Punjab.

The present study identified a minor proportion of double heterozygous cases for HbS and HbD Punjab, representing 0.01% (two cases), a finding not observed in other investigations.

Conclusion

The study underscores the significant prevalence of hemoglobinopathies among anaemic patients in the Eastern Maharashtra region, emphasising the utility of HPLC as a reliable diagnostic tool. Hemoglobinopathies, including β -thalassemia, sickle cell disease, and other variants, were found

to be major contributors to anaemia in this population, necessitating increased awareness, early detection, and tailored management strategies.

These findings highlight the need for systematic screening programs in high-risk regions to facilitate timely diagnosis and genetic counselling, ultimately reducing the burden of hereditary anaemia.

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